

***PERSUASIVE COMMUNICATION STRATEGIES AS A MANDATORY
COMPONENT IN TRAINING MASTER'S DEGREE STUDENTS
MAJORING IN INFORMATION, LIBRARY AND ARCHIVAL STUDIES***

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Modern challenges to increasing the quality of higher education require mastering relevant students' levels of English in all fields of knowledge of their future professional activity. In this context, the problem of implementing professional subjects into the curricula of master's degree students is of great interest. It is very important for them to apply their knowledge and skills to achieve professional success in Ukraine and abroad.

The course "Persuasive Communication Strategies" was taught for master's degree students as an optional subject for 3 years, but taking into account its popularity among students it was decided to include it as a mandatory discipline for master's degree students majoring in Information, Library and Archival Studies.

The purpose of the discipline is to form a system of theoretical knowledge and applied skills of students to develop their persuasive communication skills so that to ensure effective communication in the academic and professional environment and achieve personal and professional success in life.

There are some objectives of the course including the study of the following:

- advanced persuasive communication strategies used in interpersonal communication, including persuasion principles, persuasion strategy (campaign planning and research), persuasion tactics (copywriting, website design, etc.);
- social impact of persuasive campaigns;

– creation and evaluation of convincing messages, development of critical thinking, mastering the rules of persuading anyone in oral and written communication (self-presentation, public speaking and influencing people, etc., advertising copywriting, etc.).

After studying the course students must acquire the following competencies as their abilities to motivate people and realize a common goal; to generate new ideas (creativity); to identify, pose and solve problems; to work in a team to solve professional problems; as well as to improve the level of information culture permanently.

In addition, among their expected learning outcomes are: to form strategies for system organization, modernization, and improving the management effectiveness of professional activities in Information, Library and Archival Studies.

The content of the course consists of two modules.

The first module is devoted to theoretical aspects of persuasive communication and includes four themes, which will be described below.

The first theme is Persuasive Communication Strategies as a study discipline where is highlighted the scientific apparatus of the discipline, the basic concepts of the course, its place among other sciences, and its significance for academic and professional activities. The theme of practical training within the theme is devoted to conceptual guidelines of the discipline for academic and professional activities.

In the 2nd theme, students can know about the rhetorical foundations of communication, particularly about ethos, pathos, logos as the main ways of convincing the audience; basic laws of rhetoric; argumentation as a component of convincing communication. The practical training theme here is the classical rhetorical canon's main stages and components.

The 3rd theme of the 1st Module is devoted to the basics of the speaker's interaction with the audience by paying attention to functions and requirements

for speakers; strategies and tactics of the speaker which is very important for any professional kind of activity. During the theme, practical training concerns basic interaction techniques between the speaker and the audience.

Taking into account the common problem of the availability of fear of speaking 4th theme is devoted to glossophobia as an obstacle to convincing communication including the nature of the phobia of public speaking; stages of glossophobia; techniques for overcoming glossophobia. During their practical training, students learn to overcome the fear of public speaking.

The content of 2nd module, Applied Aspects of persuasive communication, consists of four themes too.

1st theme is devoted to communicative skills of public speaking, in particular types of self-presentation, oral and documentary presentation (summary and interview), the latest forms of self-presentation; reframing perception for meetings; modern media in self-presentation. During practical training students master skills of basic strategies of self-presentation.

When learning 2nd theme students can know everything about presentation as an important tool of public communication including types of presentations; persuasiveness of presentations; speech, stylistic and communicative principles of presentation; media in presentations which they can master during their practical training concerning presentations in public speaking;

Theme 3 is devoted to the persuasiveness of public speaking, in particular to methods of persuasion; psychology of influence; protection against manipulation; speechwriting techniques. And at their practical classes, students can all possibilities to practise diversification of public speeches in the persuasion of the audience

And, at last, 4th theme is geared toward copywriting as a component of convincing communication that allows students to know about functions and requirements for copywriters; basic copywriting techniques; advertising copying in convincing communication; media copywriting technologies. All students are

involved in using copywriting to convince the target audience during their practical training.

The mandatory course Persuasive Communication Strategies allows master's degree students majoring in Information, Library and Archival Studies to master not only soft skills, which are in employers' demands but also to realize their potential in professional careers for Ukraine's prosperity.